

Generation of ruthenium(IV)-oxo species and their utilization in oxidation of different substrates

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Ruthenium(IV)-oxo species constitute a family of complexes that are known particularly for their oxidizing ability. Synthesis of molecular complexes having a Ru^{IV}=O moiety is relatively easy and straight forward, and is usually achieved via a two-electron two-proton transfer reaction of a Ru^{II}-OH₂ precursor. The ruthenium(IV)-oxo species are generated *in situ*, and also in isolable form. They are heavily utilized for stoichiometric as well as catalytic oxidation of a wide variety of substrates. A brief account on the synthesis of ruthenium(IV)-oxo complexes and their utilization in oxidation of selected substrates is presented in this review.

Keywords: Ruthenium(IV)-oxo species, generation, utilization in oxidation reactions.

1. Introduction

There has been immense interest in ruthenium catalyzed reactions¹. Ruthenium has a wide range of oxidation states, from 0 to +8, which are manifested in its complexes, and each of these oxidation states is useful for bringing about catalytic transformation of selected types. Herein we wish to talk about

the generation of Ru^{IV}-oxo species, and their utilization as efficient oxidizing agent in reactions of selected types.

As +4 is a relatively higher oxidation state of ruthenium, Ru^{IV}-oxo species are used as oxidizing agent, which themselves undergo a two-electron reduction (usually associated with addition of two protons) during oxidation of the substrate, to form the corresponding ruthenium(II)-aquo species. A recognized oxidant is then used to regenerate the Ru^{IV}-oxo species to make the oxidation catalytic. This simple, yet very effective, strategy is illustrated in Scheme 1. In some cases regeneration of Ru^{IV}=O from Ru^{II}-OH₂ turns out to be not possible under the experimental condition necessary for oxidation of the substrate, rendering the oxidation to be non-catalytic or, in other word, stoichiometric. We shall describe oxidation of both types, catalytic and stoichiometric, in the following sections.

Scheme 1. Catalytic oxidation of substrates using Ru^{IV}=O species.

2. Synthesis of Ru^{IV}-oxo species

The Ru^{IV}-oxo complexes are generated, either *in situ* or in isolable form, usually starting from a suitable ruthenium(II) precursor. The most convenient protocol utilizes a ruthenium(II) starting complex having a Ru^{II}-Cl fragment, where the remaining five coordination sites of the metal center are occupied by a combination of either chelating tridentate and bidentate ligands or monodentate and chelating bidentate

ligands (depicted respectively as $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-L-L})(\text{L-L})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{L-L})_2(\text{L})\text{Cl}]^+$, where L-L-L, L-L and L represent neutral tridentate, bidentate and monodentate ligands respectively)².

Though a large variety of such tridentate, bidentate and monodentate ligands have been used so far for this purpose, a combination of 2,2':6',2''-terpyridine (abbreviated as **trpy**) as the tridentate ligand and 2,2'-bipyridine (abbreviated as **bpy**) as bidentate ligand is regarded to mark the beginning of such studies³. These ligands are known to form stable chelates with ruthenium(II), which are shown in Chart 1. The starting compound, $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})(\text{bpy})\text{Cl}]^+$, can be easily synthesized from the commercially available $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and isolated in good yield as crystalline salt. This complex has also been characterized by its crystal structure determination⁴.

Chart 1. The trpy and bpy ligands, and their coordination modes.

Stepwise synthesis of $[\text{O}=\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{trpy})(\text{bpy})]^{2+}$, starting from $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{trpy})(\text{bpy})\text{Cl}]^+$, is illustrated in Scheme 2. In the initial step, the coordinated chloride is taken out with the help of Ag^+

affording the Ru^{II}-aquo species. A two-electron oxidation of the metal center, associated with transfer of two protons, is then brought about by an appropriate oxidizing agent, furnishing the desired Ru^{IV}=O species.

Scheme 2. Generation of Ru^{IV}=O species.

3. Oxidations using Ru^{IV}-oxo species

Owing to the relatively facile reduction of ruthenium(IV)-oxo species, they are utilized as oxidants in a wide variety of reac-

tions, both catalytic and stoichiometric⁵⁻¹⁰. Selected examples of such oxidations are highlighted below.

3.1. Oxidation of phosphine

In 1981 Meyer and coworkers first reported an efficient Ru^{IV}=O mediated oxo-transfer of triphenylphosphine leading to formation of triphenylphosphine oxide¹¹. This oxidation took place via a reaction between triphenylphosphine and the selected oxo ruthenium complex, *viz.* [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{IV}=O]²⁺, in acetonitrile medium as shown below.

Meyer *et al.* also described the mechanistic details of the observed oxygenation of triphenylphosphine. The oxidation proceeds through two distinct steps. Initially a rapid oxo-transfer reaction between [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{IV}=O]²⁺ and PPh₃ takes place to generate [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{II}-OPPh₃]²⁺ as an identifiable intermediate, which then undergoes relatively slow solvolysis to furnish [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{II}-NCCH₃]²⁺ and triphenylphosphine oxide as the final products (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Stepwise oxidation of PPh₃ using [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{IV}=O]²⁺.

The initial redox step might have different mechanistic possibilities. One of them proposes a nucleophilic attack of PPh₃ on Ru(IV) center followed by migration of the coordinated phosphorous to oxo group. However, taking up seventh coordination site of ruthenium by PPh₃ seems unfavorable from steric ground¹². Similarly the outer sphere one-electron transfer possibility in initial redox step was also ruled out on kinetic ground. Not only that, discrete one-electron reduction of Ru(IV)-center within the coordination sphere was also found to be unrealistic¹³. Finally, on the basis of observed kinetic study, the initial redox step was described to proceed via a pre-equilibrium association of [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{IV}=O]²⁺ and PPh₃¹¹.

3.2. Oxidation of dialkyl sulfides

Controlled oxidation of dialkyl sulfides to the corresponding sulfoxides is considered to be an important chemical transformation. Such reactions are also known to be mediated/catalyzed by ruthenium(IV)-oxo complexes. In 1986 Meyer *et al.* reported the stoichiometric oxo-transfer reaction for dimethyl sulfide using the same oxo ruthenium species, *viz.* [(bpy)₂(py)Ru^{IV}=O]²⁺, used for oxidation of PPh₃¹⁴.

The dimethyl sulfoxide formation sequence has also been elaborated with plausible mechanistic justification as shown in Scheme 4 below. The above oxygenation process was found to proceed via three distinct steps. Initially a rapid oxo-transfer reaction takes place between $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}]^{2+}$ and dimethyl sulfide to generate an O-coordinated sulfoxide intermediate, $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}-\text{O}=\text{S}(\text{CH}_3)_2]^{2+}$. This O-coordinated sulfoxide intermediate then isomerizes to form S-coordinated sulfoxide complex, $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}-\text{S}(=\text{O})(\text{CH}_3)_2]^{2+}$. Finally, due to the solvolysis of S-coordinated sulfoxide complex free $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SO}$ is released in the solution along with formation of $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^{2+}$. As observed in the oxidation of PPh_3 , here also the possibility of seventh coordination of $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ moiety with $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ during initial redox step, as well as possibility of outer sphere electronic coupling leading to pre-equilibrium association of reactants, are ruled out due to lack of evidences.

Scheme 4. Stepwise oxidation of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ using $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}]^{2+}$.

In 1988, Takeuchi *et al.* reported the oxidation of dibutyl sulfide, $(C_4H_9)_2S$, by $[(bpy)_2(PR_3)Ru^{IV}=O]^{2+}$ in CH_3CN ¹⁵. In this reaction both the initial reduction of Ru(IV)-oxo and the final solvolysis by acetonitrile were too rapid to detect the O-bound sulfoxide intermediate spectroscopically. The steric hindrance posed by the bulky phosphine ligand in the O-bound sulfoxide intermediate, $[(bpy)_2(PR_3)Ru^{II}(O=S(C_4H_9)_2)]^{2+}$, is the reason for its rapid dissociation into the final products.

In contrast to the above stoichiometric oxidations, catalytic oxidation of aryl/alkyl sulfides by ruthenium-porphyrin complex (such as $Ru^{II}Por$; where, "Por" depicts the porphyrinato dianion) in the presence of selective oxidant is also reported¹⁶.

The oxidation of thioanisole was catalyzed by ruthenium porphyrin complexes of type $[Ru^{II}(\text{TMP})(\text{CO})]$ (TMP = 5,10,15,20-tetramesitylporphyrinato dianion), $[Ru^{II}(\text{TPFPP})(\text{CO})]$ (TPFPP = 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)porphyrinato dianion), etc., as pre-catalyst and iodobenzene diacetate as the sacrificial oxidant under visible light irradiation (Scheme 5). Here, $Ru^{II}(\text{CO})Por$ pre-catalyst initially gets converted to $Ru^{II}Por$ in the presence of visible light, and this is followed by oxidation of $Ru^{II}Por$ with $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ to generate $Ru^{IV}(\text{O})Por$. This reactive porphyrin coordinated oxo-ruthenium species catalytically oxidizes thioanisole to its corresponding sulfoxide.

3.3. Oxidation of water

Catalytic oxidation of water to dioxygen is considered to be a very useful and industrially important reaction, where oxo-ruthenium complexes are heavily utilized as catalyst¹⁷. Meyer

Scheme 5. Ru-catalyzed oxidation of thioanisole in presence of PhI(OAc)_2 .

et al. first introduced a blue oxo-bridged dimeric ruthenium(III) complex, *viz.* *cis, cis*- $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{bpy})_2]^{4+}$, for the catalytic oxidation of water¹⁸. The successive electron and proton loss generates a reactive intermediate, $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{O})\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}\text{ORu}^{\text{V}}(\text{O})(\text{bpy})_2]^{4+}$, which in turn is attacked by water molecule to form oxygen. However, due to its incompetent nature, this catalyst (blue dimer) has restricted use in catalytic water oxidation¹⁹. In 2005, Thummel reported a mononuclear ruthenium complex having the bis-naphthyridyl-pyridine ligand as water oxidation catalyst²⁰. Water oxidation by single site $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}_2$ catalysts, such as $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})(\text{bpm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})(\text{bpz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ (where bpm = 2,2'-bipyrimidine; bpz = 2,2'-bipyrazine), has also been explored²¹.

From our laboratory we were also able to contribute in this area, where we utilized a bidentate N,N-donor ligand, *viz.* 2-(phenylazo)pyridine (abbreviated as **pap**) in combination with 2,2':6',2''-terpyridine (trpy)^{22,23}. The pap ligand is known to

form stable five-membered chelate with ruthenium (see below). A mixed-ligand ruthenium(II)-aquo complex of type $[(\text{trpy})(\text{pap})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ ($\text{pap} = 2\text{-(phenylazo)pyridine}$) was synthesized, and starting from this aquo complex, the corresponding $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ species, *viz.* $[(\text{trpy})(\text{pap})\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{O})]^{2+}$, was

generated using Ce^{4+} as the oxidant in acidic medium ($\text{pH}=1\text{-}4$), which was found to spontaneously produce molecular oxygen from water with simultaneous generation of the same Ru^{II} -aquo complex that we started with, and the catalytic cycle thus continued (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6. Catalytic oxidation of water by $[(\text{trpy})(\text{pap})\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{O})]^{2+}$.

Catalytic water oxidation is truly an attractive area of research. Several reviews on this topic have appeared in the literature highlighting the different approaches to reach the target, and also providing mechanistic insights of the observed reactions^{24,25}. In addition to chemical and photochemical water oxidation, electrocatalytic water oxidation is a convenient alternative for generation of molecular oxygen from water²⁶.

3.4. Oxidation of olefin

Epoxidation of olefin is another important reaction where $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ species find wide application as oxidant. In 1986, Meyer *et al.* reported the epoxidation of a group of olefins, *viz.* styrene, norbornene, stilbene, etc., by $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}(\text{O})]^{2+}$ in acetonitrile medium²⁷. They also illustrated the mechanistic pathway based on spectroscopic studies.

The epoxidation was found to proceed through two steps. Initially $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{py})\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{O})]^{2+}$ reacted with the olefin to form an epoxide-bound ruthenium(II) species, which on solvolysis generated the epoxide (Scheme 7).

Besides stoichiometric approach, the oxo-ruthenium(IV) complexes are also used as catalyst to epoxidize the olefins. Balavoine *et al.* reported the catalytic epoxidation of alkene in presence of RuCl_3 , 2,2'-bipyridine and NaIO_4 , where *in situ* generation of $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}=\text{O}$ species was speculated²⁸. The catalytic oxidation of cyclohexene and styrene was carried out using

Scheme 7. Mechanistic pathway for quantitative epoxidation of alkene.

ruthenium(II) complexes of type $[\text{Ru}(\text{py})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ as catalyst. The nature of oxidized products, (epoxide, alcohol and aldehyde/ketone) was observed to depend on the nature of solvent and sacrificial oxidant used in the reaction²⁹. Ruthenium(IV)-oxo complexes derived from ruthenium(II) complexes of type $[\text{Ru}(\text{babp})(\text{dmsO})\text{L}]$ (where $\text{babp} = 6,6'$ -bis(benzoylamino)-2,2'-bipyridinato and $\text{L} = \text{dmsO}$ or heterocycles), were also successfully utilized as catalyst for epoxidation of olefins using iodosylbenzene, PhIO, as the sacrificial oxidant³⁰.

4. Conclusions

This brief review has illustrated the different ways to generate oxo-ruthenium(IV) species, either *in situ* or in isolable forms, and their effective utilization for both non-catalytic and catalytic oxidation of (i) phosphines to phosphine-oxides, (ii) sulfides to sulfoxides, (iii) water to dioxygen, and (iv) olefin to epoxide. In case of catalytic oxidation, sacrificial oxidants of

different types are found to be used. In certain cases, nature and quantity of the products of oxidation are observed to be sensitive to the nature of solvent used for the reaction and also on the nature of the sacrificial oxidant.

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Prof. Samaresh Bhattacharya did his B.Sc. (Chemistry Honours) and M.Sc. (Chemistry) from Jadavpur University, Kolkata. He did his Ph.D. under the guidance of Prof. Animesh Chakravorty at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata. He carried out his postdoctoral research at the University of Colorado at Boulder, USA, under the mentorship of Prof. Cortlandt G. Pierpont. He joined the Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Kolkata.

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His research is focused primarily on the coordination chemistry of the platinum group of metals, with particular emphasis on organometallic chemistry and catalysis. He has so far 154 publications in different journals, and has produced 30 Ph.D.s.

In recognition of his research contribution Prof. Bhattacharya has received the following honors and awards:

- Received the S. S. Bhatnagar Prize in 2005
- Received bronze medal from the Chemical Research Society of India in 2006
- Elected Fellow of the Indian Academy of Sciences in 2006
- Elected Fellow of the West Bengal Academy of Science & Technology in 2008
- Awarded the Ramanna Fellowship of DST in 2009
- Received the “Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Award for the year 2019” from the Indian Chemical Society.